

Supplementary Material for "Across the Loss Landscape with Progressive Growth"

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1 Proofs for Section 2

In this appendix we prove the results stated in our theoretical analysis. Throughout, we fix a basin index i and a stage t when no confusion is possible. We write

$$f_i^* := f(\theta_i^*), \quad H_i := \nabla^2 f(\theta_i^*),$$

and denote by

$$\mu_i := \lambda_{\min}(H_i), \quad L_i := \lambda_{\max}(H_i)$$

the extreme eigenvalues of the local Hessian. For $\alpha > 0$, we also introduce the quadratic ellipsoid

$$E_{i,\alpha} := \left\{ \theta_i^* + \delta : \frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq \alpha \right\}.$$

Let us remind the main assumptions and results below.

Assumption 1 (Local regularity). *For each minimum θ_i^* ,*

$$\nabla f(\theta_i^*) = 0, \quad H_i := \nabla^2 f(\theta_i^*) \succ 0.$$

Moreover, the Hessian is locally Lipschitz: there exist $r_i > 0$ and $\rho_i > 0$ such that, for all $\theta, \theta' \in B(\theta_i^, r_i)$,*

$$\|\nabla^2 f(\theta) - \nabla^2 f(\theta')\| \leq \rho_i \|\theta - \theta'\|.$$

Proposition 1 (Local ellipsoidal approximation). *Under Assumption 1, there exist constants $c_{1,i}, c_{2,i} > 0$ and $\varepsilon_i^{\max} > 0$ such that, for all $0 < \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_i^{\max}$,*

$$\left\{ \theta_i^* + \delta : \frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq c_{1,i} \varepsilon \right\} \subset \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon} \subset \left\{ \theta_i^* + \delta : \frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq c_{2,i} \varepsilon \right\}.$$

Theorem 1 (Effective curvature under frozen constraints). *Under Assumption 1, for b in a neighborhood of 0,*

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) = \frac{1}{2} b^\top \Sigma_{i,t} b + O(\|b\|^3),$$

where

$$\Sigma_{i,t} = H_{i,bb}^{(t)} - H_{i,ba}^{(t)} (H_{i,aa}^{(t)})^{-1} H_{i,ab}^{(t)}$$

is the Schur complement of the Hessian block matrix in the coordinates (a, b) .

Theorem 2 (Local accessibility law). *Under Assumption 1, assume that the frozen offset $b_{i,t}^0 = V_t^\top (\theta^0 - \theta_i^*)$ has a continuous density $p_{i,t}$ in a neighborhood of 0, conditional on (U_t, V_t) . Then, as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$,*

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{A}_t \cap \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon} \neq \emptyset \mid U_t, V_t) = p_{i,t}(0) \kappa_{p_t} (2\varepsilon)^{p_t/2} \det(\Sigma_{i,t})^{-1/2} (1 + o(1)),$$

where κ_{p_t} denotes the volume of the unit ball in \mathbb{R}^{p_t} .

1.1 A local Taylor estimate

We begin with the standard second-order Taylor expansion with cubic remainder.

Lemma 1 (Taylor expansion with cubic remainder). *Under Assumption 1, for every δ such that $\|\delta\| \leq r_i$,*

$$f(\theta_i^* + \delta) = f_i^* + \frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta + R_i(\delta),$$

where

$$|R_i(\delta)| \leq \frac{\rho_i}{6} \|\delta\|^3.$$

Proof. Taylor's theorem with integral remainder gives

$$f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^* = \frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta + \int_0^1 (1-s) \delta^\top (\nabla^2 f(\theta_i^* + s\delta) - H_i) \delta ds.$$

The remainder is therefore

$$R_i(\delta) = \int_0^1 (1-s) \delta^\top (\nabla^2 f(\theta_i^* + s\delta) - H_i) \delta ds.$$

By Assumption 1,

$$\|\nabla^2 f(\theta_i^* + s\delta) - H_i\| \leq \rho_i s \|\delta\|.$$

Hence

$$|R_i(\delta)| \leq \int_0^1 (1-s) \|\delta\|^2 \cdot \rho_i s \|\delta\| ds = \frac{\rho_i}{6} \|\delta\|^3.$$

1.2 Proof of Proposition 1

We first show that, for sufficiently small radii, the loss is comparable to its quadratic model.

Proof (Proof of Proposition 1). Choose

$$\bar{r}_i := \min\left\{r_i, \frac{3\mu_i}{2\rho_i}\right\},$$

with the convention that $3\mu_i/(2\rho_i) = +\infty$ when $\rho_i = 0$. For every δ with $\|\delta\| \leq \bar{r}_i$, Lemma 1 gives

$$f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^* = \frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta + R_i(\delta), \quad |R_i(\delta)| \leq \frac{\rho_i}{6} \|\delta\|^3.$$

Since

$$\delta^\top H_i \delta \geq \mu_i \|\delta\|^2,$$

the choice of \bar{r}_i implies

$$\frac{\rho_i}{6} \|\delta\|^3 \leq \frac{\rho_i \bar{r}_i}{6} \|\delta\|^2 \leq \frac{\mu_i}{4} \|\delta\|^2 \leq \frac{1}{4} \delta^\top H_i \delta.$$

Therefore, for all $\|\delta\| \leq \bar{r}_i$,

$$\frac{1}{4} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^* \leq \frac{3}{4} \delta^\top H_i \delta. \quad (1)$$

Next, because θ_i^* is a strict local minimum and the annulus

$$\mathcal{A}_i := \{\theta_i^* + \delta : \bar{r}_i \leq \|\delta\| \leq r_i\}$$

is compact and does not contain θ_i^* , the continuous function

$$\theta \mapsto f(\theta) - f_i^*$$

attains a strictly positive minimum on \mathcal{A}_i . Let

$$\eta_i := \inf_{\bar{r}_i \leq \|\delta\| \leq r_i} (f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^*) > 0.$$

Set

$$\varepsilon_i^{\max} := \eta_i.$$

Fix now $0 < \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_i^{\max}$. If $\theta_i^* + \delta \in \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon}$, then by definition

$$f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^* \leq \varepsilon \leq \eta_i.$$

Hence necessarily $\|\delta\| < \bar{r}_i$, for otherwise the point would lie in the annulus where the loss gap is at least η_i . We may therefore apply (1).

For the inner inclusion, suppose that

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq \frac{2}{3} \varepsilon.$$

Then

$$f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^* \leq \frac{3}{4} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq \varepsilon,$$

so $\theta_i^* + \delta \in \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon}$.

For the outer inclusion, suppose that $\theta_i^* + \delta \in \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon}$. Then

$$f(\theta_i^* + \delta) - f_i^* \leq \varepsilon,$$

and (1) yields

$$\frac{1}{4} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq \varepsilon,$$

that is,

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta^\top H_i \delta \leq 2\varepsilon.$$

Thus

$$E_{i,\frac{2}{3}\varepsilon} \subset \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon} \subset E_{i,2\varepsilon}.$$

This proves the claim with $c_{1,i} = 2/3$ and $c_{2,i} = 2$.

1.3 Preliminaries for the reduced problem

Let

$$g(a, b) := f(\theta_i^* + U_t a + V_t b),$$

and write the Hessian of g at $(a, b) = (0, 0)$ in block form:

$$\nabla^2 g(0, 0) = \begin{pmatrix} H_{aa}^{(t)} & H_{ab}^{(t)} \\ H_{ba}^{(t)} & H_{bb}^{(t)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Because $[U_t \ V_t]$ is orthogonal,

$$\nabla^2 g(0, 0) = [U_t \ V_t]^\top H_i [U_t \ V_t],$$

so it is symmetric positive definite whenever H_i is. In particular, the principal block $H_{aa}^{(t)}$ is positive definite, and the Schur complement

$$\Sigma_{i,t} = H_{bb}^{(t)} - H_{ba}^{(t)} (H_{aa}^{(t)})^{-1} H_{ab}^{(t)}$$

is also positive definite.

The next lemma records the local Taylor expansion of g .

Lemma 2 (Taylor expansion of the reduced coordinates). *There exists a constant $C_{i,t} > 0$ such that, for (a, b) sufficiently close to $(0, 0)$,*

$$g(a, b) - g(0, 0) = \frac{1}{2} a^\top H_{aa}^{(t)} a + a^\top H_{ab}^{(t)} b + \frac{1}{2} b^\top H_{bb}^{(t)} b + R(a, b),$$

with

$$|R(a, b)| \leq C_{i,t} \|(a, b)\|^3,$$

and

$$\nabla_a g(a, b) = H_{aa}^{(t)} a + H_{ab}^{(t)} b + r(a, b), \quad \|r(a, b)\| \leq C_{i,t} \|(a, b)\|^2.$$

Proof. This is a direct consequence of Lemma 1 applied to the composition

$$(a, b) \mapsto \theta_i^* + U_t a + V_t b.$$

Since $[U_t \ V_t]$ is orthogonal, this map preserves Euclidean norms, and the local Lipschitz bound on the Hessian of f transfers to g .

1.4 Proof of Theorem 1

Proof (Proof of Theorem 1). For notational simplicity, write

$$H_{aa} := H_{aa}^{(t)}, \quad H_{ab} := H_{ab}^{(t)}, \quad H_{ba} := H_{ba}^{(t)}, \quad H_{bb} := H_{bb}^{(t)}.$$

Because $H_{aa} \succ 0$, the equation

$$\nabla_a g(a, b) = 0$$

can be solved locally for a as a function of b . By the implicit function theorem, there exists a neighborhood of 0 and a unique C^1 map $a(b)$ such that

$$\nabla_a g(a(b), b) = 0, \quad a(0) = 0.$$

Define

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) = g(a(b), b) - g(0, 0).$$

We first estimate $a(b)$. By Lemma 2,

$$0 = \nabla_a g(a(b), b) = H_{aa}a(b) + H_{ab}b + r(a(b), b),$$

with

$$\|r(a(b), b)\| \leq C\|(a(b), b)\|^2.$$

Rearranging,

$$a(b) = -H_{aa}^{-1}H_{ab}b - H_{aa}^{-1}r(a(b), b).$$

Since $a(0) = 0$ and a is continuous, shrinking the neighborhood if necessary gives

$$\|a(b)\| \leq C_1\|b\|$$

for $\|b\|$ small enough. Substituting this back into the previous display yields

$$a(b) = -H_{aa}^{-1}H_{ab}b + O(\|b\|^2).$$

Now expand $g(a(b), b) - g(0, 0)$ using Lemma 2:

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) = \frac{1}{2}a(b)^\top H_{aa}a(b) + a(b)^\top H_{ab}b + \frac{1}{2}b^\top H_{bb}b + R(a(b), b).$$

Because $a(b) = O(\|b\|)$, the remainder satisfies

$$R(a(b), b) = O(\|b\|^3).$$

Substituting

$$a(b) = -H_{aa}^{-1}H_{ab}b + O(\|b\|^2)$$

into the quadratic part gives

$$\frac{1}{2}a(b)^\top H_{aa}a(b) + a(b)^\top H_{ab}b + \frac{1}{2}b^\top H_{bb}b = \frac{1}{2}b^\top (H_{bb} - H_{ba}H_{aa}^{-1}H_{ab})b + O(\|b\|^3).$$

Therefore

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) = \frac{1}{2}b^\top \Sigma_{i,t}b + O(\|b\|^3),$$

with

$$\Sigma_{i,t} = H_{bb} - H_{ba}H_{aa}^{-1}H_{ab}.$$

This is exactly the claimed expansion.

1.5 A local comparison for the compatibility set

We now compare the compatibility set

$$\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon) = \{b : \varphi_{i,t}(b) \leq \varepsilon\}$$

to the ellipsoid associated with $\Sigma_{i,t}$.

Lemma 3 (Ellipsoidal comparison for $\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)$). *Let*

$$\mathcal{E}_{i,t}(\alpha) := \left\{ b : \frac{1}{2} b^\top \Sigma_{i,t} b \leq \alpha \right\}.$$

Then there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that, for all sufficiently small ε ,

$$\mathcal{E}_{i,t}((1 - C\sqrt{\varepsilon})\varepsilon) \subset \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon) \subset \mathcal{E}_{i,t}((1 + C\sqrt{\varepsilon})\varepsilon)$$

for some constant $C > 0$ independent of ε .

Proof. By Theorem 1,

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) = \frac{1}{2} b^\top \Sigma_{i,t} b + r(b), \quad |r(b)| \leq C_0 \|b\|^3$$

for $\|b\|$ sufficiently small. Let

$$\underline{\lambda}_{i,t} := \lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{i,t}) > 0.$$

Choose $\delta > 0$ small enough that

$$|r(b)| \leq \frac{1}{4} \underline{\lambda}_{i,t} \|b\|^2 \quad \text{whenever } \|b\| \leq \delta.$$

Then, for $\|b\| \leq \delta$,

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) \geq \frac{1}{2} \underline{\lambda}_{i,t} \|b\|^2 - \frac{1}{4} \underline{\lambda}_{i,t} \|b\|^2 = \frac{1}{4} \underline{\lambda}_{i,t} \|b\|^2.$$

Since $\varphi_{i,t}(0) = 0$ and 0 is a strict local minimum, the compact sphere $\{b : \|b\| = \delta\}$ has strictly positive minimum value under $\varphi_{i,t}$. Hence, for ε sufficiently small, every $b \in \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)$ satisfies $\|b\| < \delta$, and therefore

$$\|b\| \leq 2\sqrt{\varepsilon/\underline{\lambda}_{i,t}}.$$

Consequently,

$$|r(b)| \leq C_1 \varepsilon^{3/2} \quad \text{for all } b \in \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon),$$

for some constant $C_1 > 0$.

Now define $\eta_\varepsilon := C_1 \sqrt{\varepsilon}$. If

$$b \in \mathcal{E}_{i,t}((1 - \eta_\varepsilon)\varepsilon),$$

then

$$\frac{1}{2} b^\top \Sigma_{i,t} b \leq (1 - \eta_\varepsilon) \varepsilon.$$

Moreover $\|b\| = O(\sqrt{\varepsilon})$, so $|r(b)| \leq \eta_\varepsilon \varepsilon$ for ε small enough. Hence

$$\varphi_{i,t}(b) \leq (1 - \eta_\varepsilon) \varepsilon + \eta_\varepsilon \varepsilon = \varepsilon,$$

which proves the left inclusion.

Conversely, if $b \in \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)$, then

$$\frac{1}{2} b^\top \Sigma_{i,t} b \leq \varphi_{i,t}(b) + |r(b)| \leq \varepsilon + \eta_\varepsilon \varepsilon = (1 + \eta_\varepsilon) \varepsilon,$$

which proves the right inclusion.

1.6 Proof of Theorem 2

Proof (Proof of Theorem 2). Fix the stage t and condition on the chosen subspace (U_t, V_t) . In this conditional setting, the random variable $b_{i,t}^0$ has density $p_{i,t}$ in a neighborhood of 0, and

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{A}_t \cap \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon} \neq \emptyset \mid U_t, V_t) = \mathbb{P}(b_{i,t}^0 \in \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon) \mid U_t, V_t) = \int_{\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)} p_{i,t}(b) db.$$

We first compute the volume of $\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)$. By Lemma 3,

$$\mathcal{E}_{i,t}((1 - C\sqrt{\varepsilon})\varepsilon) \subset \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon) \subset \mathcal{E}_{i,t}((1 + C\sqrt{\varepsilon})\varepsilon).$$

The exact volume of $\mathcal{E}_{i,t}(\alpha)$ is

$$\text{Vol}(\mathcal{E}_{i,t}(\alpha)) = \kappa_{p_t} (2\alpha)^{p_t/2} \det(\Sigma_{i,t})^{-1/2}.$$

Therefore

$$\text{Vol}(\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)) = \kappa_{p_t} (2\varepsilon)^{p_t/2} \det(\Sigma_{i,t})^{-1/2} (1 + O(\sqrt{\varepsilon})).$$

Next, because $\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)$ shrinks to $\{0\}$ as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and $p_{i,t}$ is continuous at 0,

$$\sup_{b \in \mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)} |p_{i,t}(b) - p_{i,t}(0)| \rightarrow 0.$$

Hence

$$\int_{\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)} p_{i,t}(b) db = p_{i,t}(0) \text{Vol}(\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon)) + o(\text{Vol}(\mathcal{B}_{i,t}(\varepsilon))).$$

Combining the two displays yields

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{A}_t \cap \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon} \neq \emptyset \mid U_t, V_t) = p_{i,t}(0) \kappa_{p_t} (2\varepsilon)^{p_t/2} \det(\Sigma_{i,t})^{-1/2} (1 + o(1)),$$

which is the claimed asymptotic law.

1.7 Remark on the Gaussian case

If, conditional on (U_t, V_t) , the initialization is isotropic Gaussian,

$$\theta^0 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_d),$$

then

$$b_{i,t}^0 = V_t^\top (\theta^0 - \theta_i^*) \sim \mathcal{N}(-V_t^\top \theta_i^*, \sigma^2 I_{p_t}),$$

so

$$p_{i,t}(0) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-p_t/2} \exp\left(-\frac{\|V_t^\top \theta_i^*\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right).$$

The accessibility law from Theorem 2 then becomes

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathcal{A}_t \cap \mathcal{L}_{i,\varepsilon} \neq \emptyset | U_t, V_t) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-p_t/2} \exp\left(-\frac{\|V_t^\top \theta_i^*\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \kappa_{p_t}(2\varepsilon)^{p_t/2} \det(\Sigma_{i,t})^{-1/2} (1+o(1)).$$

This makes explicit the energy–entropy tradeoff discussed in the main text: minima are favored when they are both close to the initialization in the frozen coordinates and broad along those directions.

2 Additional Experimental Details

2.1 Transition metrics

For two consecutive stage solutions $\theta^{(t)}$ and $\theta^{(t+1)}$, we consider the linear interpolation

$$\theta_\alpha = (1 - \alpha)\theta^{(t)} + \alpha\theta^{(t+1)}, \quad \alpha \in [0, 1].$$

Let $\ell(\theta)$ denote the evaluation loss used for transition diagnostics. In our experiments, ℓ is the cross-entropy loss evaluated on the validation set, using a fixed number of batches for efficiency.

The *interpolation barrier* is defined as the maximal excess loss along this path relative to the worse endpoint,

$$\text{Barrier}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}) = \max_{\alpha \in [0,1]} \ell(\theta_\alpha) - \max\{\ell(\theta^{(t)}), \ell(\theta^{(t+1)})\}.$$

By construction, the barrier is nonnegative.

We also consider the signed loss difference between the two endpoints,

$$\text{EndpointGap}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}) = \ell(\theta^{(t+1)}) - \ell(\theta^{(t)}),$$

and its absolute value,

$$\text{EndpointAbsGap}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}) = |\ell(\theta^{(t+1)}) - \ell(\theta^{(t)})|.$$

For interpretability, we additionally report the positive and negative parts:

$$\text{EndpointImprovement} = \max\{0, \ell(\theta^{(t)}) - \ell(\theta^{(t+1)})\},$$

$$\text{EndpointDegradation} = \max\{0, \ell(\theta^{(t+1)}) - \ell(\theta^{(t)})\}.$$

Retention is a binary indicator of whether the transition remains in a low-barrier regime. Given a fixed threshold $\tau > 0$, we define

$$\text{Retention}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}) = \mathbf{1}\left\{\text{Barrier}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}) \leq \tau\right\}.$$

In all deep-learning experiments, we use $\tau = 0.1$.

Leakage is defined as the complement of retention,

$$\text{Leakage}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}) = 1 - \text{Retention}(\theta^{(t)}, \theta^{(t+1)}).$$

Thus, leakage is also binary: it indicates whether a transition leaves the retained low-barrier regime.

For each transition, we also record the full interpolation profile, the maximum loss attained along the path, and the value of α at which this maximum occurs.

2.2 Restricted curvature metrics

To characterize the local geometry of stage transitions, we estimate Hessian quantities on restricted parameter subspaces. Given a binary mask $m \in \{0, 1\}^d$, we define masked Hessian-vector products by projecting both the input direction and the output onto the masked coordinates.

For each post-expansion solution, we estimate the top restricted Hessian eigenvalue λ_{\max} using power iteration; the restricted trace using a Hutchinson estimator; and stochastic log-determinant estimates through a Lanczos-based approximation when needed.

The main paper reports the top eigenvalue and trace-based quantities. These quantities are computed on two masks, namely the *active subspace*, i.e., the parameters already trainable at the current stage; and the *newly released subspace*, i.e., the parameters that become trainable when moving from stage t to stage $t + 1$. We also report the dimensions of these masks and, when useful, the trace normalized by the number of active parameters.

2.3 CIFAR-100 / ResNet-18 setup

All deep-learning experiments are conducted on CIFAR-100. We use the standard train/test split and further divide the original training set into train and validation subsets using a fixed 90/10 split. This yields approximately 45,000 training examples and 5,000 validation examples, while the test set contains the standard 10,000 examples. Training data use standard CIFAR-style augmentation: random crop with padding 4, random horizontal flip, tensor conversion, and channel-wise normalization. Validation and test data use only tensor conversion and normalization. The normalization constants are the standard CIFAR-100 statistics $\mu = (0.5071, 0.4867, 0.4408)$, $\sigma = (0.2675, 0.2565, 0.2761)$.

Our default architecture is a CIFAR-style ResNet-18. It consists of a 3×3 convolutional stem with stride 1, followed by four residual stages with block

counts $[2, 2, 2, 2]$, channel widths 64, 128, 256, 512, global average pooling, and a final linear classifier.

Optimization uses SGD with Nesterov momentum. The main hyperparameters are: learning rate: 0.1, momentum: 0.9, weight decay: 5×10^{-4} , label smoothing: 0, total number of epochs: 100. We use cosine annealing over the full training horizon. Automatic mixed precision is enabled. The training batch size is 128, while evaluation uses batch size 256.

The main ResNet experiments compare a full-model baseline with all parameters trainable from the start; progressive growth schedules with $S \in \{3, 5, 10\}$ stages; with two growth triggers: validation accuracy and training loss. Unless stated otherwise, the patience parameter is set to 2 epochs. The main ResNet results are averaged over 3 random seeds.

2.4 Progressive growth mechanism

Our practical growth mechanism is implemented by assigning each trainable tensor to a sequence of stage groups. For convolutional and linear layers, this grouping follows the first tensor dimension, which corresponds to output channels or output units. Roughly speaking, stage t activates approximately $(t + 1)/S$ of the coordinates, up to discrete effects due to tensor shape.

The final classifier layer is kept active from the first stage. Batch-normalization parameters and running statistics are grouped consistently with the corresponding feature groups whenever possible, so that normalization variables are released together with the channels they control. Parameters not covered by these structured cases are assigned stage groups at random.

At each optimization step, frozen parameters are clamped to their initialization values and their gradients are masked to zero. The same masking is applied to optimizer states of matching shape. Frozen floating-point buffers, including batch-normalization running statistics, are likewise restored to their initial values. Operationally, this implements the affine-slice interpretation used in the theory: at each stage, optimization is restricted to the active coordinates while the frozen complement remains fixed at initialization.

2.5 Internal control protocols

The full-model baseline trains the same architecture with all parameters active from initialization. Fixed-subspace training uses the same initial active subspace as progressive growth, but never releases the frozen complement. One-shot unfreezing also starts from the same initial constrained submodel, but releases all remaining parameters in a single transition. Progressive growth releases the same total set of parameters over multiple transitions. These controls separate three effects: training a restricted submodel, delaying capacity release, and gradually relaxing constraints.

2.6 Algorithmic summary

The practical procedure used in the deep-learning experiments can be summarized as follows.

1. Initialize the full network parameters θ^0 .
2. Partition trainable tensors into S nested stage groups. For convolutional and linear layers, groups are formed along the output-channel or output-unit dimension. The classifier is active from the first stage.
3. Activate the first group and freeze all remaining parameters at their initialization values.
4. Train the active parameters using the chosen optimizer while clamping frozen parameters, frozen buffers, gradients, and matching optimizer states to their frozen values.
5. Monitor the growth criterion, either validation accuracy or training loss.
6. When the criterion has not improved for the specified patience, save the pre-expansion solution, release the next parameter group, and continue optimization from the current weights.
7. After each expansion, compute transition diagnostics between the pre-expansion and post-expansion stage solutions: interpolation barrier, retention, leakage, endpoint gap, and restricted curvature on the active and newly released subspaces.
8. Repeat until all groups have been released. At test time, the final model is the full architecture.

2.7 Stage selection and transition evaluation

For each stage, we track a stage-dependent best checkpoint according to the chosen trigger:

- for the `val_acc` trigger, the stage metric is validation accuracy;
- for the `train_loss` trigger, the stage metric is the negative training loss.

If the stage metric does not improve for a number of epochs equal to the patience parameter, growth advances to the next stage. In the main experiments, stage transitions are determined by this patience-based rule. The internal control experiments with validation-accuracy growth use the same patience-based rule, without forcing stage transitions at predetermined epochs. The best validation checkpoint over the full run is used for final reporting.

When a stage transition occurs, we compare:

- the pre-expansion checkpoint, i.e., the model immediately before releasing new parameters;
- the best checkpoint obtained after re-optimizing in the expanded subspace.

All transition metrics are computed between these two endpoints.

For interpolation-based diagnostics, we evaluate the loss on 11 equally spaced points along the segment between the two endpoints. To reduce cost, transition losses are computed on at most 2 batches of the validation loader. The same transition protocol is used throughout the reported deep-learning experiments.

2.8 Hessian estimation details

Restricted Hessian metrics are computed using a single batch drawn from a dedicated non-augmented training loader. The Hessian batch size is 128. In the main configuration, the estimators use 10 power-iteration steps for λ_{\max} , 4 Hutchinson probes for the trace, 2 stochastic Lanczos probes for the log-determinant, 8 Lanczos steps, damping 10^{-3} . The main paper relies primarily on λ_{\max} and trace-based quantities.

2.9 Patience ablation

For the aggressive $S = 10$ regime, we additionally study the effect of patience on stage stability. In the training-loss-triggered experiments, we evaluate patience values $p \in \{1, 2, 5\}$, while keeping all other optimization and data settings identical to the main ResNet experiments.

2.10 MLP control experiment

To test whether the curvature effect observed in ResNet is specific to convolutional residual architectures, we run a controlled experiment with an overparameterized fully connected MLP on a hard two-moons classification task. The dataset contains 1200 training examples and 3000 test examples, with noise level 0.30. The MLP has four hidden layers with width 256. We compare full-model training, fixed-subspace training, one-shot unfreezing, and progressive growth.

All methods reach comparable test accuracy, around 91.5%–91.7%, indicating that the growth procedure does not materially affect predictive performance in this simple setting. Interpolation barriers are also nearly zero for all growth variants, suggesting that the task does not induce strongly separated stage-wise solutions. However, the restricted-curvature signal is clear: one-shot unfreezing yields $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{new}}/\lambda_{\max}^{\text{act}} = 0.5733 \pm 0.1552$, whereas progressive growth yields 0.1691 ± 0.0938 for $S = 5$ and 0.1142 ± 0.0329 for $S = 10$. Thus, even in a fully connected overparameterized model, progressive growth releases directions that are substantially flatter than the already active subspace. This supports the interpretation that the growth-induced curvature bias is not specific to residual convolutional networks.

2.11 Schedule sensitivity.

Forced expansion schedules preserve the qualitative curvature contrast between one-shot and progressive growth, but can degrade final accuracy and increase interpolation barriers. This confirms that the timing of constraint relaxation matters: the curvature bias induced by progressive growth is robust qualitatively, but its effect on transition stability and predictive performance is schedule-dependent.

Table 1: Controlled MLP experiment on a two-moons classification task. All methods achieve comparable test accuracy and nearly zero interpolation barriers, reflecting the simplicity of the task. Nevertheless, progressive growth releases directions with substantially lower restricted curvature than one-shot unfreezing, suggesting that the curvature effect is not specific to convolutional residual architectures.

Method	Test acc. (%) \uparrow	Barrier ($\times 10^{-2}$) \downarrow	Retention \uparrow	Leakage \downarrow	$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{new}}/\lambda_{\max}^{\text{act}}$ \downarrow
Full MLP	91.58 ± 0.16	–	–	–	–
Fixed subspace, $S = 5$	91.50 ± 0.37	–	–	–	–
One-shot unfreeze, $S = 5$	91.72 ± 0.14	0.00 ± 0.00	1.0000 ± 0.0000	0.0000 ± 0.0000	0.5733 ± 0.1552
Progressive growth, $S = 5$	91.60 ± 0.12	0.02 ± 0.03	1.0000 ± 0.0000	0.0000 ± 0.0000	0.1691 ± 0.0938
Progressive growth, $S = 10$	91.53 ± 0.14	0.00 ± 0.00	1.0000 ± 0.0000	0.0000 ± 0.0000	0.1142 ± 0.0329

Disclosure of Generative AI Use

A generative AI tool was used in a limited manner to improve the readability of the manuscript, including grammar correction and stylistic editing. It was not used to generate scientific claims, results, proofs, experiments, figures, or references. All technical content, interpretations, and conclusions were produced and verified by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final manuscript.